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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO HIGHLIGHT THE
IMPORTANCE OF ANATOMY AS A SUBJECT: AN OPINION-
BASED SURVEY CONDUCTED ON STUDENTS &
PHYSIOTHERAPIST****¹Dr. Sidra Anum, ¹Dr. Muhammad Asim Shahzad, ²Dr. Sajawal Yousof**
¹THQ Hospital Gojra, ²Rural Health Center Fazil Pur, Rajan Pur**Abstract**

Objective: The objective of the study was to indicate and highlight the significance of anatomy as a subject for physiotherapists or students.

Methodology: This research study was organized at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. The time duration for this study was from February to December 2017. In this study, both students and physiotherapists were registered with Pakistan physical therapy association. For the assemblage of information, a survey proforma was sex questions were included in the assessment of data.

Results: Between the students and physiotherapists, 500 questionnaires were divided. Out of these, the questionnaire was correctly completed by 286 (57.2%). Different viewpoint was collected. The number of respondents who thought anatomy could be learned by repeated readings, teaching videos were essential for the study of anatomy, performing dissection is important and only clinical anatomy should be studied were 89 (31.11%), 259 (90.55%), 204 (71.32%) and 155 (54.38%) respectively. Moreover, 179 (62.58%) and 280 (97.9%) participants through anatomy were not an easy subject to remember and anatomy was significant in physical therapy respectively.

Conclusion: The current study concluded that for medical professionals, anatomy is an important subject although it is not an easy subject.

Keywords: Anatomy, Physical Therapy, Dissection, Future Option, Clinical Practice.

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INTRODUCTION:

The great word anatomic give rise to word anatomy. Anatomia is a word come from anatemnein which mean “to cut up” or ‘cut open’. In the course of the 1st year, along with the medical and allied health subjects, which include dentistry, nursing, speech pathology and doctor of physical therapy (DPT), the subject of physical therapy (DPT), the subject of anatomy is added [1]. After the department of secure practice in the medical field, there observed on eventual reduction in the teaching of anatomy. In the few previous years. Whereas, for many years, the subject of anatomy has been considered essential in the medical syllabus [2 – 4]. Anatomy a difficulty after excluding anatomy from the medical course. A public programme, the number of people who were of the view that doctors should have encounter human anatomy, was 94% [5]. Quality of surgeons is influenced because the subject of anatomy is not focused [6]. Doctors must have information regarding the subject of anatomy. It is helpful in many ways. It helps in the application of various procedures for treatment and in association with other professional guiding the patients. Moreover, it also helps in the composition of differential indication and to organize clinical assessment. The technique of dissection has been best and convenient in reaching. But, in the present era, a method of teaching anatomy has been advanced. Different techniques are added to it. These include the use of 3D imaging computer learning, use of models, the teaching of living and radiology anatomy, inspection of the pre-dissected specimen and didactic teaching [7]. In the field of medicine, there observed a high trend of group learning. There are many advantages of team-based learning (TBL). As through interacting, we learn more. During the preclinical years, interdisciplinary and integrated curses are established by the medical school. In order to keep in mind, the procedures of gross anatomy, team-based learning is very advantageous. The participants of groups should be regular and prepared well [8]. Nowadays, anatomists are very rare. So, in UK and USA, the subject of anatomy is taught by medical doctors and surgeons respectively. In medical schools, anatomy is taught by doctors only [9 – 11]. There are many important and less important factors due to which teaching as a career is affected. The standard of living interest and income also affect the career selection among medical students. But these factors are not important as such. The main factors due to which teaching as a career is affected. The standard of living interest and income also affect the career selection among medical students. But

these factors are not important as such. The main factors include the interest and passion of subject, teaches as a role model and passion of subject, teaches as a role model and elevation of career. During the training of career. During the training of house job, most medical doctors get involved in this specialty. Their career selection is influenced by it [9].

SUBJECTS & METHODS:

This research study was organized at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. The time duration for this study was from February to December 2017. In this study, both students and physiotherapists were included. The number of DPT students were 400 and physiotherapists registered with Pakistan physical therapy association were 700. The formula $N=N/1+N/2$ was used for the measurement of sample size. For the assemblage of information, a survey proforma was designed and filled by participants. Six questions were included in the proforma. Each question had three choices; A (agree), B (disagree) and C (do not know). SPSS was used for the assemblage of data.

RESULTS:

Between the students and physiotherapists, 500 questionnaires were divided. The number of the possible questionnaires was 1,100. Out of 500, the questionnaire was correctly completed by 286 (57.2%) subjects. The number of undergraduate DPT and BSC. Physiotherapy students and post-professional doctor of physical therapy (PPDPT) practitioners were 205 (71.67%) and 81 (28.32%) respectively. The number of respondents who thought anatomy could be learned by repeated readings, teaching videos were necessary for the study of anatomy, performing dissection is important and only clinical anatomy should be studied were 89 (31.11%), 256 (90.55%), 204 (71.32%) and 155 (54.38%) respectively. Moreover, 179 (62.58%) and 280 (97.9%) participants thought anatomy was not an easy subject to remember and anatomy was significant in physical therapy, anatomy as a difficult subject, clinical study of anatomy and requirement of dissection for understanding anatomy were 6 (2%), 103 (36%) and 128 (44.75%), 87 (27%) respectively. The people who did not give any suggestion were 21 (7.3%). Ultimate cases who considered that through repeated readings, anatomy could be learned, were 89 (31.11%). Still, there were some people who disagreed with the above statement. The number of such people was 150 (52.44%).

Table: Response to different questions in relation to their qualification

Questions	Response	Under Graduate (205)		Post Graduate (81)		P-Value
		No	%	No	%	
Anatomy is an important subject in physical therapy.	Agree	200	97.6	80	98.8	0.522
	Disagree or Don't know	5	2.4	1	1.2	
Anatomy is difficult to understand and retain.	Agree	126	61.5	53	65.4	0.532
	Disagree or Don't know	79	38.6	28	34.6	
Anatomy should only be studied as clinical anatomy.	Agree	96	46.8	59	72.8	< 0.001
	Disagree or Don't know	109	53.2	22	27.1	
Performing dissection is helpful in understanding and retaining Anatomy.	Agree	155	75.6	49	60.5	0.001
	Disagree or Don't know	50	24.4	32	39.5	
Teaching videos are essential for Anatomy.	Agree	182	88.8	77	95.1	0.186
	Disagree or Don't know	23	11.2	4	4.9	
Anatomy is memorized by multiple readings	Agree	71	34.6	18	22.2	0.041
	Disagree or Don't know	134	65.4	63	77.8	

DISCUSSION:

For the physiotherapists, the outcomes of the current study highlight the significance of techniques for teaching anatomy. In the practice of physiotherapy. In the practice of physiotherapy, the base is formed by clinical anatomy [12]. The importance of anatomy as a necessary subject in medical course can't be

denied. Its importance was considered by 98% people whereas, the people who disagreed were just 2%. In Nigeria, a similar research study was organized. According to this research study, out of 353 subjects, 98% agreed with this statement [9]. In another research, according to statements of students of the first year, understanding of anatomy was not that

easy. On the other hand, 36% of subjects considered anatomy easy but 64% did not agree. Students preferred anatomy because it is a good learning technique as show the three-dimensional view of internal structures and positions that were hard to understand otherwise. In our study, the importance of dissection is considered by 71.23% participants [5]. It is necessary to conduct more research to conduct more research studies on anatomy, as in up-coming medical professionals, the knowledge of anatomy is more significant [13]. For the teaching of anatomy, there is a great significance of teaching videos. This fact is considered by 90.55% subjects. In learning and remembrance of information related to anatomy, visual information is important. In order to verify and affirm the suspicion, it is essential to organize more research studies.

CONCLUSION:

The study illustrated that in order to understand the information related to anatomy, the subject of anatomy is very helpful. So, in medical and allied professions, the subject of anatomy is important, although is very hard. In the earliest times, demonstrations, lectures, visual help and problems-based laboratory sessions, were used for delivering the anatomical more similar research studies with a greater number of people involved.

REFERENCES:

1. Oluwatoyin O, Uvie O, Grace A. The prospect of anatomy as a career choice among clinical year medical students in Nigeria. *Ann Afr Med* 2009; 8:90-4.
2. Willan PL, Whitmore I, Humpherson JR. Career progress of temporary lecturers in anatomy: A surgical success story. *Clin Anat* 1998;11: 50-4.
3. Anand MK, Raibagkar CJ, Ghediya SV, Singh P. Anatomy as a subject and career option in view of medical students. *J Anat Soc* 2004; 53:10-4.
4. Lee HB, Allison G, editors. A comparative study of the presentation of anatomy by lectures versus ICAL packages to physiotherapy students. *Proceedings of the International Interactive Multimedia Symposium*; 1992.
5. Winkelmann A. Anatomical dissection as a teaching method in medical school: a review of the evidence. *Med Educ* 2007; 41:15-22.
6. Turney B. Anatomy in a modern medical curriculum. *Ann Royal Coll Surg Engl* 2007; 89:104.
7. Older J. Anatomy: a must for teaching the next generation. *Surgeon* 2004; 2:79-90.
8. Kerby J, Shukur ZN, Shalhoub J. The relationships between learning outcomes and methods of teaching anatomy as perceived by

medical students. *Clin Anat* 2011; 24: 489-97.

9. Vasani NS, DeFouw DO, Compton S. A survey of student perceptions of team-based learning in anatomy curriculum: Favorable views unrelated to grades. *Anat Sci Educ* 2009; 2:150-5.
10. Vishnumaya G, Ramnarayan K. An appraisal of anatomy teaching and learning by undergraduate nursing students in a multi-professional context: a study done at a medical school. *Bratislavské lekárske listy* 2009; 110: 506.
11. Collins TJ, Given RL, Hulsebosch CE, Miller BT. Status of gross anatomy in the U.S. and Canada: Dilemma for the 21st century. *Clin Anat* 1994; 7:275-96.
12. Utting M, Willan P. What future for dissection in courses of human topographical anatomy in universities in the UK? *Clin Anat* 1995; 8:414- 7.
13. Cottam WW. Adequacy of medical school gross anatomy education as perceived by certain postgraduate residency programs and anatomy course directors. *Clin Anat* 1999; 12:55-65.